

We provide a potential prompt for medical entity matching.

System Message:

You are an expert in the medical domain.

User Message:

Goal: given the medical text, select the most appropriate entity from the list of entities provided for a given entity.

Text: The patient's symptoms of painful shoulder movement, particularly at mid-range (80° to 120°), worsening at night, and without any observed effusion or abnormality on X-ray, suggest subacromial bursitis. Subacromial bursitis is characterized by inflammation of the bursa under the shoulder's acromion, leading to pain during abduction between 60° and 120°, which aligns well with the patient's reported range of painful movement. Other conditions like cervical radiculopathy, osteoarthritis, polymyalgia rheumatica, and pseudogout typically present differently in terms of both symptoms and examination findings.

List of Entities: ['Limited shoulder movement', 'Shoulder pain', 'Limited shoulder flexion', 'Shoulder impingement', 'Limited shoulder abduction', 'Shoulder subluxation', 'shoulder impingement syndrome', 'shoulder joint', 'shoulder nerve', 'Shoulder dislocation'].

Select the most appropriate entity from the list of entities to replace 'painful shoulder movement' in the text. Only output the entity name. No additional information is required.
